

Sum of Series of Binomial Coefficients

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents a summation of series of binomial coefficients in combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial coefficient

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-10]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-10] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series and $V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!}$.

Theorem 2.1: $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

Proof. $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \implies V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$,

where $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r = V_{n-1}^{r+1}$.

Let us prove that $V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r &= \frac{(n-1+r+1)!}{(n-1)!(r+1)!} + \frac{(n+r)!}{r!n!} = (n+r)! \left(\frac{n}{n!(r+1)!} + \frac{r+1}{n!(r+1)!} \right) \\
&= \frac{(n+r)!(n+r+1)}{n!(r+1)!} = \frac{(n+r+1)!}{n!(r+1)!} = V_n^{r+1}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

For example, $V_0^4 + V_1^4 + V_2^4 + V_3^4 = V_3^5 \Rightarrow V_2^5 + V_3^4 = V_3^5$.

$$V_2^5 + V_3^4 = \frac{(2+5)!}{2!5!} + \frac{(3+4)!}{3!4!} = 7! \left(\frac{3}{3!5!} + \frac{5}{3!5!} \right) = 7! \left(\frac{8}{3!5!} \right) = \frac{(3+5)!}{3!5!} = V_3^5.$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a binomial theorem was constituted on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series. This new idea can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2020) Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics. *hal-0286583*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9p4ek>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2020) Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics. *hal-02862222*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9re5>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Combinatorial Identities for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Novel Binomial Series and its Summations. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4078523>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Successive Partition Method for Binomial Coefficient in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7060159>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) Partition of Multinomial Coefficient. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7063004>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) A Generalized Method for proving the Theorem derived from the Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7047548>.
- [8] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and its Applications. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v22>.

- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.
- [10] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials and Integers for Applications in Computing and Cryptography. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.